

CREATING PRE-, WHILE-, AND POST-LISTENING ACTIVITIES: A STRUCTURED APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14271946>

Abstract: Listening is a pivotal skill in language learning, requiring well-designed pedagogical strategies to foster comprehension and engagement. This study explores the development and implementation of pre-, while-, and post-listening activities, guided by key theoretical insights. Drawing from Ur (1984), Rost (1990), Anderson and Lynch (1991), Flowerdew and Miller (2005), and Lynch (2004), this paper evaluates strategies to enhance learner outcomes through systematic activity planning.

Key words: Pre-listening activities, while-listening activities, post-listening activities, listening comprehension, schema activation, real-time processing, note-taking.

Introduction

Listening is not merely a passive process but an active cognitive endeavor essential for acquiring second language proficiency. Effective listening pedagogy involves activities that scaffold learning before, during, and after listening tasks. Pre-listening activities aim to activate prior knowledge and set a purpose for listening; while-listening activities focus on maintaining engagement and extracting meaning; post-listening activities consolidate understanding and encourage further application. This paper examines these stages in detail, incorporating insights from seminal works in listening pedagogy.

Methodology

A qualitative review of theoretical frameworks and practical strategies was conducted, analyzing approaches from the five aforementioned sources. The study categorizes listening activities into pre-, while-, and post-listening stages, highlighting their theoretical underpinnings and practical implementations.

Results

1. Pre-Listening Activities

Pre-listening activities prepare learners for the listening task, enhancing their ability to process auditory information effectively.

Ur (1984) emphasizes the importance of setting context and goals to lower anxiety and increase focus. Flowerdew and Miller (2005)

advocate for activating schema through brainstorming, discussions, or vocabulary previews.¹ Strategies include prediction exercises, visual aids, or questioning. For instance, learners might be shown images or asked to predict content based on a title.

2. While-Listening Activities

While-listening activities sustain engagement and facilitate comprehension.

Anderson and Lynch (1991) highlight that real-time processing requires tasks that focus attention on key details. Rost (1990) underscores interactive listening as a dynamic way to enhance retention.² Examples include gap-filling exercises, sequencing tasks, or note-taking.

¹ Flowerdew, John, and Miller, Lindsay. *Second Language Listening: Theory and Practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005.

² Rost, Michael. *Listening in Language Learning*. New York: Longman, 1990.

Learners might identify keywords, complete sentences, or answer guided comprehension questions as they listen.

3. Post-Listening Activities

Post-listening activities reinforce understanding and provide opportunities for extended learning.

Lynch (2004) suggests that these activities encourage reflection and application, solidifying language skills.³ Flowerdew and Miller (2005) argue for integration with speaking and writing skills to deepen comprehension. Techniques include summarizing, role-playing, or group discussions. Learners might write a summary, participate in debates, or create follow-up projects based on the listening content.

Discussion

The division of listening tasks into pre-, while-, and post-listening stages ensures a holistic approach to skill development. Integrating these stages supports cognitive processing, maintains motivation, and caters to diverse learner needs. However, successful implementation depends on careful selection of activities that align with learner proficiency and task objectives.

Conclusion

Developing effective pre-, while-, and post-listening activities is essential for fostering listening comprehension in language learning. By drawing on established theories and incorporating practical strategies, educators can design lessons that enhance engagement, understanding, and application. Further research could explore the impact of digital tools and adaptive technologies on these activities.

References:

1. Ur, Penny. Teaching Listening Comprehension. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1984.
2. Rost, Michael. Listening in Language Learning. New York: Longman, 1990.
3. Anderson, Ann, and Lynch, Tony. Listening. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1991.
4. Flowerdew, John, and Miller, Lindsay. Second Language Listening: Theory and Practice. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005.
5. Lynch, Tony. Study Listening. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004.

³ Lynch, Tony. Study Listening. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004.